

COMPOSITION OF PRUSSIAN AND TURNBULL'S BLUES. PART V. RÔLE OF HYDROLYSIS AND THEIR COMPOSITIONS.

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It has been observed in several samples of Prussian and Turnbull's blues, prepared under wide range of dilutions of the mixed reactants at a definite temperature that the composition of Prussian blue is much affected by its hydrolysis, while Turnbull's blue is much less affected, because of the presence of an excess of acid in ferrous sulphate. By extrapolation of the values of CN/Fe against the dilutions of the mixed constituents, a probable ratio of Fe:CN for Prussian and Turnbull's blues of identical composition has been obtained.

It was suggested in a previous publication (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1933, 213, 240) that the composition of Prussian and Turnbull's blues may be slightly changed through hydrolysis of the precipitated product during repeated washing, or during long dialysis inside a parchment bag. It had also been reported by Ghosh, Dhar and others (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 659) that colloidal Prussian blue gets partially hydrolysed during dialysis and ageing and produces some ferric hydroxide according to the reaction,

With a view to studying how far the composition of these blues is altered or influenced by the dilution of iron and ferrocyanogen salts, several samples of Prussian and Turnbull's blues were prepared under a wide range of dilution of the mixed reactants at a definite temperature and the analytical results have been discussed in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Solutions of ferric chloride, potassium ferrocyanide, ferrous sulphate, and potassium ferricyanide of concentrations $M/5$, $M/10$ and $M/100$ were prepared and samples of Prussian and Turnbull's blues were prepared by mixing the corresponding iron and ferrocyanogen salts at each of the above concentrations in equivalent proportion. The samples were thoroughly washed free of soluble impurities, as far as possible, and their compositions determined by estimating the total iron and cyanogen radical per 100 g. of the substance.

Ferric chloride was prepared in pure distilled water while ferrous sulphate had to be acidified with dilute sulphuric acid to prevent its

hydrolysis and consequent oxidation by atmospheric oxygen. The blue precipitates were filtered free from soluble impurities as far as possible and dried by means of an air-oven in Buchner funnels. The precipitates, when dry, were finely powdered in an agate mortar and preserved in dry and clean tubes for analysis.

TABLE I.
Prussian blue.
Temp. = 35°.

Conc. of FeCl ₃ .	Conc. of K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ .	Total Fe.	Total (CN).	Fe:CN.
M/5	M/5	32.820%	38.075%	1:2.50
M/10	M/10	35.245	39.530	1:2.41
M/25	M/25	33.790	37.140	1:2.368
M/50	M/50	37.050	40.830	1:2.373

TABLE II.
Turnbull's blue.
Temp. = 35°.

Conc. of FeSO ₄ .	Conc. of K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆ .	Total Fe.	Total (CN).	Fe:CN.
M/5	M/5	32.08%	36.64%	1:2.46
M/10	M/10	32.01	36.60	1:2.46
M/25	M/25	30.86	35.54	1:2.49
M/50	M/50	31.20	36.23	1:2.50
M/100	M/100	30.42	35.34	1:2.50

DISCUSSION.

From the foregoing tables and the curves drawn by extrapolating the values of CN/Fe against the concentrations of the reactants, mixed together for preparing the blues, it will be evident that the compositions of the Prussian and Turnbull's blues are undoubtedly affected by the dilution of the reacting solutions. It has already been discussed in previous communications that the phenomena of hydrolysis and of adsorption, together, have some influence on the composition of these blues; this will be supported from the order of change in the ratio of Fe:CN that takes place with the dilution of the reactants. The solution of ferrous sulphate being acidic due to the presence of dilute sulphuric acid, effects of hydrolysis will evidently be much less in the case of Turnbull's blue. In the preparation of Prussian blue, aqueous solutions of ferric chloride and potassium ferrocyanide were mixed together, and hence hydrolysis was relatively more marked in this case than in the case of Turnbull's blue.

From the observations recorded in Table I, sufficient support to our views regarding the influence of hydrolysis on the composition of Prussian blue has been obtained. Gradually the ratio CN:Fe diminishes as the dilutions are increased, which shows that iron, as ferric hydroxide, adds to the total iron content of the compound, although a part of the cyanogen may be lost as soluble $H_4Fe(CN)_6$, according to

The above equation further suggests that more of Fe as $Fe(OH)_3$ is retained by the compound than what is lost by it as soluble $H_4Fe(CN)_6$.

In Table II the observations are otherwise. The ratio of Fe:CN gradually decreases with dilution and tends to reach a limit (1:2.5) at higher dilution. In the case of Prussian blue, too, the limiting value of Fe:CN (1:2.37) is reached at higher dilution. When the curves are drawn on the same scale, it is further observed that the compositions of Prussian and Turnbull's blues are probably identical at such concentration of the respective reactants as is represented by the point of intersection of the two curves. In Table I, the value of Fe:CN at concentration $M/5$ is 1:2.5, while the value of Fe:CN at concentration $M/10$ is 1:2.41. It is likely, therefore, that at a concentration of the respective reactants between $M/5$ and $M/10$, say at about $M/8$, the ratio of Fe:CN would be equal to 1:2.465 as can be guessed from the point of intersection of the two curves, provided, of course, the conditions of dilution and temperature could be maintained identical in each case.

In view of the above results, it may be inferred that Prussian and Turnbull's blues tend to assume identical composition, but the secondary effects, which are of a chemical and adsorptive nature, do not allow us to determine either the exact condition, or the ratio of Fe:CN for an absolutely identical compound. It can, however, be guessed by extrapolation, that the ratio of Fe:CN would be equal to 1:2.46 at a dilution of about $M/8$ of the mixed constituents, under such conditions as were maintained during the author's investigations: and this goes to confirm the author's view regarding the influence of dilution on the compositions of Prussian and Turnbull's blues.

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